

Digital Divide in Smart Farming

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ABSTRACT

While the world population is increasing, the production of food needs to match this growing demand. Also, climate change brings more challenges for this sector. Therefore, improvement of productivity within agriculture is essential, preferably with the use of technical functions. Currently, not every agriculture farmer in The Netherlands is using the technology of smart farming, whilst these technologies make the necessary improvements possible.

This paper focuses on the factors that influence the acceptance of smart farming and to what extent these factors can be used to measure the acceptance of farmers towards smart farming in order to reduce the current digital divide. The research is conducted by a survey on a sample farmers in The Netherlands. In conclusion, the factors that can be influenced are the technical knowledge, usefulness, ease of use and attitude towards use. These factors can be positively influenced by the broader provision of information or training. With positive control of these factors, further development and higher productivity within agriculture rates are possible.

Keywords

Smart farming, agrarian culture, food production, technology acceptance, smart sensors, increasing efficiency.

INTRODUCTION

The world population is currently estimated to increase with 82 million people per year (worldometers, 2019). Hence the world population is growing, so is the demand for food. The world's food production needs to match these increasing numbers and therefore improvement of productivity within the agricultural is essential (Food and Agriculture Organization, 2009). Furthermore, the demand for more food is set against the challenges of rising climate change and more extreme weather conditions. These make it more difficult to have a qualitative and profitable harvest every year (Stahl, 2019).

Recently, Techworld pointed out the promise of growing agricultural productivity by adopting Internet of Things related technologies (Savvas, 2015). This can be seen as one of the solutions to realize a rise in productivity within agriculture. The implementation of IoT in an agricultural environment is defined by the name "Smart Farming". The characteristics of the so-called smart farms, are physical sensors (e.g. temperature, humidity, CO₂, illumination) and controllers (e.g., sprinkler, LED lights, air conditioner and heater) for monitoring and controlling the environmental conditions of the farm (Savvas, 2015). A full explanation of smart farming will be given in the theoretical framework, later in this research.

Given the fact that the world population is increasing, it is interesting to look at the implementation of smart farms. With these predictions, it is interesting to read that only 20% of the farms are investing in smart farming (Kempenaar & Kocks, 2013). These investments are merely for methods from smart farming, but this is not defined as a smart farm. This triggers to look at the reasons why farmers do not invest in their smart farm. After the interruptive factors are pointed out, there may be ways to influence these factors so all farms can contribute to the upcoming challenges.

This research will look at the occurring digital divide within the architectural environment focusing on smart farms. In 2016 it is proven that agricultural development benefits from smart agriculture (Gondchawar & Kawitkar, 2016), still not every agricultural business uses this new technology (Kempenaar & Kocks, 2013). Digital Divide is commonly defined as 'the gap between those who have and do not have access to computers and the Internet' (van Dijk, 2006). For this research, the digital divide is defined as the gap between agricultural businesses who do or do not use smart farming. Furthermore, this paper will look at the reasons why this gap occurs.

The scope of this research contains smart farming within agricultural companies in The Netherlands. Since the Netherlands is the second-largest export country for agricultural products, and therefore also has a large production of agricultural

products. The largest country for exporting agricultural products in the United States (Dolman, Jukema, & Ramaeker, 2019). This geographical location does not apply to our research, because of the varieties in regulations and laws per state. Dutch agricultural businesses work with the same laws and regulations, and are therefore a more homogenous group.

Furthermore, the time aspect is taken into account when choosing a geographical location, hence this research took place from October 2019 until December 2019.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

This research is conducted on the implementation of smart farming and the influencing factors on the ability to apply smart farming. The problem statement of this research is as follows:

“Which factors influence the acceptance of smart farming, and to what extent could these factors be used to measure the acceptance of farmers towards smart farming in order to reduce the current digital divide?”

To be able to answer this question, there are different theoretical and practical research questions on which the research focuses:

Theoretical research questions:

1. What is smart farming?
2. What are the characteristics of a farm?
3. What are the factors that influence technology acceptance?
4. What are the factors that influence technology acceptance in agriculture?

Practical research questions:

5. To what extent are the factors that influence technology acceptance related to the factors that influence the implementation of technology in agriculture?
6. How do the characteristics of an agrarian effect the technology acceptance?

RELEVANCE

Managerial Relevance

According to research from Wageningen University & Research (Kempenaar & Kocks, 2013), there are five major global challenges in which our food systems play an important role. The first one is that the world population may rise to nearly 10.5 billion by 2100. The demand for food, in particular for animal proteins, will therefore probably increase by even more than the growth in

population suggests. This is because of the so-called westernization of food diets worldwide. Improved resource efficiency is needed. The second one is the rising temperatures and changes in weather patterns that may cause flooding, droughts and disease, all of which influence food production and food safety. The agricultural sector and food systems also face major challenges related to the environment and biodiversity. The chemical revolution of the 20th century has led to an agricultural system that is essentially based on high inputs of fossil energy, synthetic fertilizers, pesticides and antibiotics. These have brought and continue to bring many advantages. In many cases, however, the effect on the environment of their excessive use (water and air quality and even public health) is not sufficiently considered when deciding whether to use these inputs. The fourth challenge is that many EU consumers eat more meat than is advisable and do not eat enough fruit and vegetables to get the intakes they require. These challenges are not a direct result of problems created by agriculture, but agriculture can be part of the solution. The last challenge is the current trends in demographics, urbanization and an increase in farm size are resulting in the empty countryside. Also, within rural areas, the population clusters in cities and large towns. This leads to questions on vital infrastructure (such as broadband for precision farming and electricity for the machines of the future) (Détang-Dessendre, Geerling-Eiff, Guyomard, & Poppe, 2018).

Academic Relevance

In this research, we investigate which characteristics of an agricultural business affect the implementation of a smart farm. We draw on research on user acceptance of computer technology (Davis, Bagozzi, & Warshaw, 1989). Using the technology acceptance model (1989) from this research, we look at the characteristics of agricultural businesses that influence the TAM. Furthermore, the level of technology acceptance influences implementing smart farm technology. The acceptance level is determined by the characteristics of this specific group, agrarians. Research on this topic has not taken place before. This can be seen as the knowledge gap we are trying to answer.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Conceptual model

Smart farming is a descendant from the words “Precision farming”. Precision farming is a form of agriculture, at which plants and animals get their needs very precisely (Kempenaar & Kocks, 2013). The short definition which describes smart farming is “Smart use of strategic business options with

technological innovations.” (Kempenaar & Kocks, 2013). But this does not tell what the definition is of “smart”. According to Kempenaar and Kocks smart is about the combination of separate parts within the company. For technology, this can be defined as the combination of smartphones, tablets, ICT, satellites, sensors, tractors, etc.

To be able to say something about the factors that influence the acceptance of technology, we look at the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) (Taherdoost, 2018).

The TAM is an extraction of the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) model. The TRA predicts and explains human’s IT usage behavior through three main components: attitudes, social norms, and intentions. The difference between both models is that TAM ignores the social influence on the adoption of technology. In this research, this is not a problem because technology is already used in agriculture, and they don’t have to adapt it for the first time (Kempenaar & Kocks, 2013). The elements that TAM uses to predict and explain human’s IT behavior are perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and attitude towards the use of smart sensors within the agriculture.

To find out which factors impede the acceptance of technology in agriculture specific, the research also looks at factors from earlier research about IoT implementation in agriculture. This is because there is limited research on the acceptance of smart farms. We look at these factors, because technology acceptance is different between specific groups with different characteristics. Agriculturists are found to be a specific group, who react different on technology compared to other industries (Kempenaar & Kocks, 2013). The elements that, according to several sources (H. Castle, D. Lubben, & D. Luck (2016), Wolfert, Ge, Verdouw, & Bogaardt (2017), Tholhuijsen (2017), Kempenaar & Kocks (2013)) limit the acceptance of smart farms are: Size of the company, financial resources, technical knowledge, geographic location, and added value (compared to the current situation). This consecution says nothing about which element is more or less important. The first element, the size of the company, has an impact on the acceptance of technology because larger companies are more in need of efficiency within their company (Kempenaar & Kocks, 2013). Financial resources are about the investment that is necessary to implement the technology. The technical knowledge is about the complexity of technology and the knowledge that is needed for the implementation and use of new technologies. Geographic location has an impact on smart farms because of logistical and safety reasons. According to several sources (H. Castle, D. Lubben, & D. Luck (2016), Wolfert, Ge, Verdouw, & Bogaardt (2017), Tholhuijsen (2017), Kempenaar & Kocks (2013)), the added value is one

of the main reasons for not implementing new technologies. Most companies are not persuaded by the value new technologies add compared to their current situation. The relations between the different variables are visualised in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Conceptual model

Hypothesis

The conceptual model in figure leads to the following hypotheses:

Main effects of characteristics on the use of smart farming

- H1. The size of the farm is positively related to the use of smart farming.
- H2. The financial resource is positively related to the use of smart farming.
- H3. The technical knowledge is positively related to the use of smart farming.
- H4. The geographical location is positively related to the use of smart farming.

Main effects of technology acceptance

- H5. The use of smart farming is higher when usefulness is bigger.
- H6. The use of smart farming is higher by higher ease of use.
- H7. The use of smart farming is higher by a positive attitude towards the use.

The moderating role of technology acceptance

- H8. The relationship between characteristics and smart farming is strengthened by higher technology acceptance.

METHOD

Because the research is about elements that influence the implementation of smart farms, the first step of the research uses qualitative data. This qualitative data is gathered by analyzing the secondary data source literature. A critical analysis of this source will give the researchers a higher level of knowledge about the researched subject (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016). The literature is to be found on the internet.

Survey research

When we look at the variables that are of importance in this research, it becomes clear that there is primary data necessary to be able to say something about the prediction of the dependent variable. The necessary primary data can be conducted with experimental research or survey research. Through the fact that the implementation of smart farming, and specifically the process before the implementation, is impossible to copy, survey research is used. A disadvantage of survey research is that the research subjects are aware that they are part of a scientific study. This may have the result that the subject answers the question differently than when it does not know that it takes part in survey research. It is not clear whether the recorded behavior or response is the same behavior that would have occurred naturally (Hox & Boeije, 2005).

Since the researchers cannot measure the whole agriculture population but want to say something about the population, a survey is used. To get useful information it is important to take the following points into account. Closed-ended questions will be used that help to make decisions quick, because of the short period that is available. Within the closed-ended questions, multi-item measures will be used because the data that is going to be gathered is not concrete. The research team will develop its own questions for the research. When developing the questions for the survey, all the elements that should be avoided are taken into account such as double negatives and leading questions. The non-comparative scale is used because it does not give a benchmark but asks the question about only one object, event or situation. People in the agricultural sector are always working outdoors, they are not working with PC's and they don't like to answer emails. Therefore the approach that is going to be used for this survey is Computer-assisted personal interview. (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016)

The questionnaire will give an introduction to why smart farming acceptance is investigated. Also, an organized structure will be present with the first questions about farmers their basic knowledge about smart farms. Secondly about issues that may appear with implementing or adopting smart farming technologies and what is keeping them from using it. And thirdly, questions about if farmers have any recommendations on how more farmers would adopt smart farming methods to make the work more efficient. Because the survey is personal, an instruction will be given to the participants and there will be guidance if there are any questions from the farmers. (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016)

To increase the response rate, different tactics will be used. First, the maximization of participants

is needed. This will increase by showing appreciation towards the farmers and personally visit the farmers. It is important to clarify that the main point of the survey is to make it easier for farmers to accept smart farming methods. Secondly, trust is required to increase the response rate (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016). Farmers need to know that the survey is confidential. Trust is also needed for open lines of communication with the participants. In the whole survey process, there will be several meetings with the participants.

First, the farmers within the sample will get a pre-notification. Then the questionnaire will take place in person. After this, a thank you will be sent and final contact will take place (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016).

DATA COLLECTION

Since the entire population of agriculture farmers consists of millions of entities around the world, it is not possible due to time and human resources within this research to produce reliable data collection about the entire population. Therefore, data collection in this research is conducted with a sample that is likely to the population. The target population of the sample in this research is the agricultural farmers in the national borders of The Netherlands. The country is divided into provinces. According to the numbers of 2018, published by CBS, there is a difference in the numbers of farmers by each province. The sample will represent the number of farmers in each province, the sort of agriculture and the farm size. The sample has a distribution similar to the real numbers of the population. For example, for the number of farmers per province, there will be more farmers from Brabant in the sample than farmers from Flevoland. Table 1 shows the number of farmers per province, table 2 shows the sort of farms and table 3 shows the size of the farms in respectively the population and sample.

Since there is no sampling frame available for the main elements of the agriculture population, the sample design is constructed based on nonprobability sampling. The findings from this research cannot be confidently generalized to the population since not all entities of the population have the probability of being chosen as sample subjects. The findings within this sampling method, however, can lead to potentially useful information regarding the population about the influencing factors of the acceptance of smart farms.

Therefore, the sample design is conducted based on convenience sampling. A relatively small sample, with a distribution similar to the population, will be interviewed during the following months during a face-to-face setting by the researchers. This is conducted as multivariate research. Since there

are 15 parameters, the sample size of this research consists of 150 agriculture farmers.

Table 1. Sample distribution agricultural farms

Province	#	% of total	Number in sample
Groningen	2570	4.77%	7
Friesland	4291	7.96%	12
Drenthe	2802	5.20%	8
Overijssel	6828	12.66%	19
Flevoland	1677	3.11%	5
Gelderland	9088	16.85%	25
Utrecht	2165	4.02%	6
Noord-Holland	3565	6.61%	10
Zuid-Holland	4663	8.65%	13

Table 2. Sample distribution agricultural farms

Sort of farm	#	% of total	Number in sample
Tillage	10844	20.11%	30
Horticulture	6746	12.51%	19
Permanent cultivation	1586	2.94%	4
Cage animals	26907	49.90%	75
Grazing animals	4631	8.59%	13
Crop combination	1155	2.14%	3
Cattle breeding	541	1.00%	2

Table 3. Sample distribution agricultural farms

Size of farm	#	% of total	Number in sample
Small	28359	52.60%	79
Medium	22865	42.41%	64
Large	2695	5.00%	7

Measures

The questionnaire contains all the items listed in table 4 in the appendix.

RELIABILITY AND VALIDITY

Measurement reliability

For multi-item measures, Cronbach's alpha can be used to check whether the set of items are interrelated. The items to measure technology acceptance are adapted from Bagozzi, Davis, and Warshaw (1989), who reported a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.63. For single-item measures, Cronbach's alpha cannot be checked.

Measurement Validity

For technology acceptance, we use measures that have been adapted from a high-quality article (e.g., Bagozzi, Davis and Warshaw (1989)). This increases the validity of the measures used in our study. The measures for the farm characteristics are new measures that we developed ourselves. Therefore validity is likely to be high because they are concrete and simple questions, measured by a Likert scale.

For technology acceptance, a multi-item measure is used because it is a more abstract construct that will never be captured completely using a single item. By using multiple items to measure this construct, the conceptual overlap between the construct acceptance and its measure is high. All other constructs are very concrete (e.g., which is your yearly return?), hence a single item will suffice.

External Validity

The external validity of this research may be low. Firstly, because there is no good sampling frame available and therefore constructed based on nonprobability sampling. Furthermore, only Dutch agricultural businesses are taken into account during this research. Hence, the results that are found in the agricultural business sample cannot automatically be generalized to not Dutch agricultural businesses.

RESULTS

In this section, the following topics will be presented: the data cleaning process, a description of the data and the findings of the research.

Data cleaning process

To analyze the data, MS Excel was used. Altogether, three surveys were conducted. During the data cleaning process, we looked at the time taken to fill in the survey, outliers, and unusual responses. Respondents who completed the survey within one minute are not considered reliable since they most likely did not take the time to think the question through. A scatterplot was used to detect outliers.

Since there were no outliers, neither unreliable responses, the data set of 3 respondents remained the final dataset.

Description of the Data

After cleaning the data, the statistics were generated. All respondents have an agricultural business in Noord-Brabant, the Netherlands. 66.7% of the respondents have a yearly return between €250.000 en €1.500.000, the other 33.3% has a yearly return of €250.000 or lower. On the question: 'I have completely implemented smart farming' 33% has answered this question with 1, 33% has answered this question with 2, and 33% has answered this question with 4 on a five-point Likert scale. The group who responded below or equal to 3 on the five-point Likert scale is considered the group 'non-users of smart farming'. The group who responded above or equal to 4 on the five-point Likert scale are considered the group 'users of smart farming'.

FINDINGS AND CONCLUSION

At the beginning of this research a couple hypotheses were set. Using the results, we are looking if the set hypotheses are true or false.

The following hypotheses were conducted false:

H1: The size of the farm is positively related to the use of smart farming.

H2: The financial resources are positively related to the use of smart farming.

H4: The geographical location is positively related to the use of smart farming.

The following hypothesis were conducted true:

H3: The technical knowledge is positively related to the use of smart farming.

H5: The use of smart farming is higher when the usefulness is bigger.

H6: The use of smart farming is higher by higher ease of use.

H7: The use of smart farming is higher by a positive attitude towards the use.

H8: The relationship between characteristics and smart farming is strengthened by higher technology acceptance.

Since the financial resources and the size of the farm were measured with the same question, and this question did not influence the use of smart farming, these hypotheses were found not true. The answers regarding the use of smart farming methods were answered differently when the size/ financial resources were the same, and therefore no positive relation was found. Since the respondents of the survey were all from the same geographical location, no conclusion could be made about hypothesis four and therefore the hypothesis was found false.

Since all respondents have given an equal answer to the question about technical knowledge, looking at the question about the use of smart farming. Meaning when one was high, the other was high. Therefore, we conclude that there is a positive relation between technical knowledge and the use of smart farming.

Hypothesis five, six and seven were also conducted true. All respondents found smart farming useful, given there was a 100% positive response. Positive response in this research is interpreted as a 4 or 5 on a five-point Likert scale. The attitude toward use has an average score of 3.9 out of 5. We see that the attitude towards use is relatively high. Anyhow, none of the respondents finds that using smart farming would make them a competitor for other agricultural businesses. The respondents who had an overall lower score on this part of the survey also claimed to not have implemented smart farming completely. Ease of use has an average of 3.33 out of 5. Since the respondents who scored low on the ease of use, also did not implement smart farming we conclude a positive result.

When we look at the definitions of the independent variables that are used, these are no variables that can be managed very well, most of the variables are within the characteristics of the farm. The technical knowledge is a variable that can be managed. This can be done with training and lectures about the subject.

Other variables, the usefulness, ease of use and attitude towards use, can increase based on the personal interest of the agrarian. When he/she is interested in the subject and gets trained with technology methods, these variables can be changed positively, which makes the agrarian more acceptable towards technology.

DISCUSSION

The research and specifically the data gathering phase, is done in a short time frame. This leads to fewer results than is valid to give an official conclusion. Another limitation is, due to the time frame, is that the research is only focused on Dutch farms and therefore not generalizable to the world. The start of the research is mainly based on a literature review. During this review, it became clear that there is little literature about the specific topic or parts of the topic available.

When looking at the research method that is used, questionnaires, we can say that some of the variables are better measured with another method. For example, the current use of smart farming methods is measured with a five-point Likert scale. This variable would be more valid when looking at all the tasks that are done on the farm, and then look at how much is done with the use of a smart farming method. Also to increase the quality of the

questioner, adding negative questions to validate all of the other answers about the subject and to make sure people really think through the questions.

The advice for future research is to use a larger sample size on which more results can be concluded. Also, some of the variables can be measured better with another measuring scale, instead of the current interval scale. Which makes the definition of these variables more reliable. For example, the size of the company and the financial resources, are now measured with the same question.

The importance of the research is already mentioned in the introduction of the paper. Because of the mentioned reasons the researchers are convinced that there must be action on this subject, whether it is with this research or other approaches on the subject.

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APPENDIX

Table 4. Measurement procedure table

Construct name	Measurement	Supporting reference
Current use of smart farming methods	I implemented smart farming totally. Five point statements 1 = 'strongly disagree'; 2 = 'disagree'; 3 = 'neutral'; 4 = 'agree'; 5 = 'strongly agree'.	Own development
Size farm/ Financial resources	Which is your yearly return? a. < 250.000 b. 250.000-1.500.000 c. >1.500.000	Own development and adapted from CBS (2019)
Technical knowledge	Four five point statements 1 = 'strongly disagree'; 2 = 'disagree'; 3 = 'neutral'; 4 = 'agree'; 5 = 'strongly agree' on the following statements: 1. My interaction with technical systems is clear and understandable. 2. It would be easy for me to become skillful at using the technical systems. 3. I would find technical systems easy to use. 4. Learning to operate technical systems is easy for me.	Adapted from: Venkatesh, Morris, Davis, & Davis, (2003)
Geographical location	In which region is your farm based? 1. Noord-Holland 2. Zuid-Holland 3. Zeeland 4. Limburg 5. Noord-Brabant 6. Friesland 7. Gelderland 8. Drenthe 9. Overijssel 10. Flevoland 11. Utrecht 12. Groningen	Own development
Usefulness	Four five point statements 1 = 'strongly disagree'; 2 = 'disagree'; 3 = 'neutral'; 4 = 'agree'; 5 = 'strongly agree' on the following statements: 1. Using smart farming methods enables me to accomplish tasks more quickly. 2. Using smart farming methods improves the quality of the work I do. 3. Using smart farming methods makes it easier to do my job. 4. Using smart farming methods enhances my effectiveness on the job. H9. 5. Using smart farming methods increases my productivity.	Adapted from: Venkatesh, Morris, Davis, & Davis, (2003)

Attitude towards use	<p>Four five point statements 1 = ‘strongly disagree’; 2 = ‘disagree’; 3 = ‘neutral’; 4 = ‘agree’; 5 = ‘strongly agree’ on the following statements: If I use smart farming methods ...</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. I will increase my effectiveness on the job. 2. I will spend less time on routine job tasks. 3. I will increase the quality of output of my job. 4. I will increase the quantity of output for the same amount of effort. 5. My fellow agrarians will perceive me as competent. 	<p>Adapted from: Venkatesh, Morris, Davis, & Davis, (2003)</p>
Ease of use	<p>Four five point statements 1 = ‘strongly disagree’; 2 = ‘disagree’; 3 = ‘neutral’; 4 = ‘agree’; 5 = ‘strongly agree’ on the following statements: The degree to which using smart farming methods is perceived as being difficult to use.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. My interaction with smart farming methods is clear and understandable 2. I believe that it is easy to get smart farming methods to do what I want it to do. 3. Overall, I believe that smart farming methods are easy to use. 4. Learning to operate smart farming methods are easy for me. 	<p>Adapted from: Venkatesh, Morris, Davis, & Davis, (2003)</p>

Table 5. Survey Questions

I know what smart farming is and what it can realize								
Strongly agree	+3	+2	+1	0	1	2	3	Strongly disagree
Strongly agree	+3	+2	+1	0	1	2	3	Strongly disagree
Strongly agree	+3	+2	+1	0	1	2	3	Strongly disagree
Strongly agree	+3	+2	+1	0	1	2	3	Strongly disagree
Assuming I had access to Smart Farming, I intend to use it								
Strongly agree	+3	+2	+1	0	1	2	3	Strongly disagree
Strongly agree	+3	+2	+1	0	1	2	3	Strongly disagree
Strongly agree	+3	+2	+1	0	1	2	3	Strongly disagree
Strongly agree	+3	+2	+1	0	1	2	3	Strongly disagree
Strongly agree	+3	+2	+1	0	1	2	3	Strongly disagree
Strongly agree	+3	+2	+1	0	1	2	3	Strongly disagree